

Emotional intelligence and personality traits in high school students: a survey study

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ABSTRACT

The capacity to regulate our emotions in unusual circumstances is known as emotional intelligence (EI). EI has been acknowledged as a predominantly major challenge to both student achievement and the big five personality (BFP) traits. This study aimed to explore the impact of EI on an individual's personality. Specifically, it sought to determine: i) the level of EI of students in form 2 and 4; ii) gender differences in EI among students in form 2 and 4; and iii) the possibility whether there is a significant relationship between aspects of emotional intelligence and BFP towards form 2 and form 4 students. This study was conducted quantitatively at a Malaysian Secondary School located in Pahang, Malaysia. A set of questionnaires was distributed to 108 respondents at the school. For ethical consideration, the researchers informed the responsible behalf such as regional education department and school, and then distributed an informed consent form to each respondent. The findings indicate that self-regulation is the highest level of personality dimension achieved which is $m=3.54$. On the other hand, there is no significant difference between genders among students in form 2 and 4 affected by EI. Besides, there is a significant relationship between aspects of EI and BFP where the Pearson coefficient, or r -value is 0.674. Future research on interventions that are more appropriate for developing students' personalities to enhance their EI should be undertaken, according to the implications of this study.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Personality plays a crucial role in the educational framework of contemporary students. A positive personality can cultivate students who possess positive ideals and thereby enhance multiple facets of academic performance. However, the need to regulate negative emotions might lead to the development of a pessimistic disposition [1]. Typically, within the realm of education, every student is unique and possesses their own personality. The personality is also indicative of their interests and inclinations, especially when these inclinations are related to their future and involve choices for academic courses or career fields, among other things [2]. When students possessing a commendable disposition harbors a distinct objective regarding their future aspirations. It implies that they have strategically devised and contemplated methods to acquire something they strongly desire. By cultivating a good personality, individuals also enhance their adaptability in various environments, including school, tuition centers, and other settings. Multiple studies have demonstrated a high correlation between personality and academic achievement [3]–[7].

It may be demonstrated that the perception of different personalities among students can enhance the efficacy of learning in the classroom. Furthermore, when teachers are able to discern the personality of students, they can enhance their comprehension of their students' traits and develop more efficient instructional strategies. In light of this circumstance, students have the opportunity to highlight their emotional intelligence (EI). There are a number of research that have been conducted in the past that investigate the connection between personality and EI [8]. EI has been observed to exhibit correlations with certain personality traits [9], with some displaying favorable correlations with EI, while others displaying negative correlations [10]. The significance of EI lies in its role as a crucial intermediary in facilitating the development of a favorable and constructive character among students during their time in school. EI can facilitate the psychological development of students through a variety of activities [11]. Previous studies [12], [13] revealed that trait EI can be regarded as a comprehensive personality characteristic that is incorporated into the upper echelons of a multi-level personality hierarchy. These results unequivocally demonstrate that EI plays a pivotal role in shaping students' personalities during their time in school [14].

Emotional intelligence is an essential prerequisite in life, but it is not given sufficient emphasis or integrated into the educational curriculum in school. Highlighting the significance of EI in various educational settings, it is a necessary step to provide a more thorough realization of individual personality development. Therefore, the educational syllabus places significant importance on the development of individual's character, which validates the consideration of students' personalities during research and teaching activities by teachers [15]. The cultivation of positive characters commences inside the educational setting. The school plays a crucial role in fostering students' potential by promoting positive character traits through a range of activities including sports, games, uniformed groups, clubs, and student organizations. Personality research undertaken in schools, including [16]–[18], have shown that personality traits have a substantial influence on many student outcomes, such as academic achievement, emotional states, and overall well-being. These traits ultimately contribute to the formation of their EI.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Emotional intelligence has generated significant interest in academic circle. It refers to the capacity to understand and regulate emotions, utilizing them as a framework for achieving productive conduct. In addition, it is crucial as it has a tremendous impact on an individual's behavior, which is a direct result of their personality. Therefore, there is a clear and direct relationship between personality and EI as shown in Figure 1. Previous study [19] demonstrated a significant correlation between EI and personality factors. This study has provided a clear explanation of how EI acts as a mediator in the formation of individual personality. In addition, previous studies have examined the idea that research on EI and personality can provide a better explanation for the difference in individuals' professional achievement compared to established measurements like intelligence quotient (IQ) [20]. It can be inferred that EI not only enhances students' academic achievements but also has a broader impact including their relationship with the environment [21]. It signifies that EI has exerted an impact on diverse individual personalities, enabling them to discern whether their behaviors are desirable or not. Previous studies have discussed how EI of individual is associated with big five personality traits (BFPT) [22], [23]. The BFPT hypothesis of personality traits is used in all personality studies related to social psychology research, and it has yielded several articles addressing numerous facets of psychology, educational science, technology, and other fields. All these five personalities can be grouped under the umbrella of BFPT [24], [25]. The aim of this study is to examine how the research gaps highlighted in previous studies regarding the relationship between EI and BFPT affect individual development, specifically in terms of academic achievement, particularly from an educational perspective.

A study [12] found that the independence variable, EI, has a positive influence on the variables of openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, and agreeableness. Additionally, it has shown a significant variance value. However, the link between EI and the dependent variable of neuroticism exhibits a negative regression. The context becomes particularly intriguing when the extraversion variable demonstrates a significant degree of variability compared to the other five factors that were evaluated. In addition, another study shows that the relationship between EI and BFPT has similar findings to the previous study [12]. The most significant correlation identified is that emotional EI influences extraversion. The extraversion variable has the lowest variant value [26]. This demonstrates that the students' personality is not impacted by EI factors such as team EI, well-being, self-control, emotionality, and sociability. Furthermore, a study examining the relationship between EI and individual personality in school settings found that the variable of conscientiousness exhibited the highest level of personal growth [27]. Furthermore, this study concludes that there is no statistically significant disparity in the various factors of BFPT based on gender. The study's findings indicate a substantial correlation between each personality characteristic of the BFPT and the EI of individuals.

Added to that, a study conducted by Ghiabi and Behsarat [28] investigated the correlation between personality traits and EI among a sample of 443 students, comprising 237 females and 206 males. The study revealed that extraversion had a positive correlation with EI, while neuroticism had a negative correlation with EI. The discovery corroborated the previous investigation [29]. They conducted a study including 304 individuals which revealed a substantial correlation between overall EI and personality traits. In a study conducted by Grehan [30], the objective was to investigate the correlation between personality traits and EI among a sample of 63 psychology students. The findings revealed a significant relationship between personality traits and EI. The variables of conscientiousness and EI had a strong correlation with the rating of the assignments. Prior research has also discovered a notable association between EI and personality traits such as extraversion, agreeableness, and conscientiousness [30]. Moreover, an examination of past research reveals that female tend to exhibit higher levels of neuroticism and agreeableness variables compared to males, while male tend to score better in extraversion and openness variables than female [31]. Furthermore, a notable disparity was observed in regard to personality traits, specifically extraversion and conscientiousness variables, with female participants scoring higher than their male counterparts in both aspects [32].

Figure 1. The application of theories in examining the relationship between EI and BFPT in enhancing students' performance

Moreover, examining the relationship between BFPT and student performance at different levels of schooling, particularly in secondary school, previous research has identified variations in results concerning factors that have a favorable or negative impact on individual personality. Interestingly, a systematic review study [33] disclosed that conscientiousness variable is the predominant personality attribute that significantly influences students' academic performance. Neuroticism variable is the personality attribute that has the least influence on students' academic performance. Individually examining empirical research reveals that conscientiousness is the primary factor that influences students' performance. Additionally, four other variables have a detrimental impact on students' development from an academic standpoint [34]–[37]. Conversely, the study by Papageorgiou *et al.* [38] demonstrated that only extraversion variable significantly impacts students' academic performance during classroom sessions. Unexpectedly, a separate prior study investigating the correlation between student personality and academic achievement in light of social media impact has similarly discovered that all variables have had an optimistic impact on student performance [39].

In conclusion, the presence of high EI in students can contribute to the development of a positive belief paradigm and self-perception. By consistently demonstrating a positive pattern in their academic practice, students can significantly enhance their chances of achieving success in their learning. This is further corroborated by a prior study that demonstrated the impact of both personality and EI abilities on students' education and productivity. The results suggest that having an outgoing personality is a very reliable indicator of academic success and should be given high importance in intervention approaches. Otherwise, students with personalities due to their positive EI demonstrate exceptional academic performance [40]. It is evident that the three variables of conscientiousness, openness, and extraversion in the BPFT have a strong positive correlation with motivation for learning. In contrast, neuroticism is negatively associated with learning attitude, making it unattractive and discouraging [41].

3. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1. General background

This study emulates a quantitative phenomenological approach within a positivist paradigm. It aims to establish a causal relationship between the present study and its dependent and independent variables [42]. A neutral and quantifiable observation of an action is within the realm of positivism, a paradigm that emphasizes reason and measurement. In order to obtain reliable data in this study, a quantitative non-experimental research design was utilized [43] to reveal secondary school students' responses to concerns about EI, BFPT, and their relationship. Hence, the quantitative data derived from the questionnaire will also assess if the gap in gender acts as an indicator for their level of personality or not.

3.2. Population and sample

The population of respondents of the present study were the students from a Malaysian Secondary School located in Pahang State. Considering this school has numerous classes, the cluster sampling approach was used to determine the number of samples. Cluster sampling is the process of selecting a random sample of clusters from the population and inviting all members of that cluster to participate [44]. Thus, to ascertain the real number of samples, researchers only examined two clusters of various groups of students, specifically those in forms 2 and 4. In order to ensure that researchers collect both clustered groups of samples, there is a systematic research ethical approach that was implemented. Finally, after passing through the steps of appointment of study samples, the final sample total is 108 students. Before the data collecting process is carried out, all samples are given an Informed Consent Form and they have understood that they are a volunteer study sample without having any element that is contradictive to research ethics.

3.3. Research instruments

The researchers employed research instruments to collect data. There are many categories of instruments based on their structure or format, function, nature, and accessibility. The predominant tools utilized in nursing studies are scales and questionnaires [45]. The researchers exclusively employed a single instrument, namely a questionnaire, in this study. Questionnaires often fulfil a role in quantitative social research. A questionnaire is a compilation of queries sent towards individuals with the purpose of collecting statistical data on a specific topic. Well-designed and implemented questionnaires can serve as a crucial instrument for establishing assertions about people, groups, or entire populations. Surveys are a highly efficient method for collecting diverse information from a large cohort of individuals, commonly referred to as respondents. A survey's efficiency hinges on correctly written questionnaires [46]. In the present study, two questionnaires were used as the Tables 1 and 2.

For these two research questionnaires, they have been adapted from two different previous studies. For the big five personality (BFP) questionnaire, it has been adapted from a study of John *et al.* [47], while the emotional intelligence (EI) questionnaire has been derived from a study of Rahman [48]. Prior to usage, these both questionnaire instruments were subjected to validity and reliability testing. Two experts in the fields of secondary school education and counselling education, respectively, were assigned to evaluate their agreement on the validity of both questionnaires using a Likert Scale. Cronbach's alpha formulation was used to assess the reliability of both measures, with the BFP questionnaire scoring 0.89 and the EI questionnaire scoring 0.72. This demonstrates that both experts agreed on all of the items that were adapted, produced, and used in this study.

Table 1. Big five personality questionnaire

Construct	Positive items	Negative items
Extraversion	1, 11, 16, 26, 36	6, 21, 31
Agreeableness	7, 17, 22, 32, 42	2, 12, 27, 37
Conscientiousness	3, 13, 28, 33, 38	8, 18, 23, 43
Neuroticism	4, 14, 19, 29, 39	9, 24, 34
Openness	5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40, 44	35, 41

Table 2. Emotional intelligence questionnaire

Construct	Distribution of items	Number of items
Self-awareness	1, 2, 3, 4, 5	5
Self-regulation	6,7,8,9,10, 11	6
Self-motivation	12,13,14,15,16, 17, 18	7
Empathy	19,20, 21, 22, 23, 24,25	7
Social Skills	26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32	7

3.4. Procedure of data collection

To ensure that the data can be obtained appropriately, the researchers have first followed guidelines and research ethics that have been defined by several parties that are responsible for protecting the data, information, and privacy of an individual. Research ethics is the best research practices that follow the key principles of ethics in protecting the rights and safety of persons and ecosystems for the goal of universal well-being while also complying with all regulations and legislation [49]. The researchers have also followed the guidelines as explained by Malaysian government in the Personal Data Protection Act 2010 where a person cannot disclose personal data [50]. This act mandates the establishment of rules for the protection of personal information in government organizations. The data's confidentiality and integrity are being examined. There are several steps implemented by the researchers to comply with the ethics of the study and it can be referred as in the Table 3.

Table 3. Procedures of conducting the study

No.	Action taken
1	Get a letter of approval to carry out the study from the university
2	Get the school's approval to conduct the study
3	Select study respondents
4	Distribute a questionnaire containing informed concern, background, and 2 sets of variable questions
5	Keep the collected data
6	Analyze the data

3.5. Procedure of data analysis

The planning, designing, data collection, analysis, inference of meaningful interpretation, and reporting of the research findings are all statistical procedures utilized in a study. Statistical analysis provides meaning to the meaningless data, giving the data a sense of significance. Only when appropriate statistical tests are applied will the results and inferences be accurate [51]. There are three types of statistical tools used in this study, namely descriptive, t-test, and Pearson correlation.

4. RESULTS

Following data collection via questionnaire distribution to respondents, three distinct findings were obtained, namely the demographics of the respondents, the respondents' views on their own personality and emotional intelligence. The research findings in this research article are only focused on three research objectives, notably the respondents' perspectives on the Big Five Theory and emotional intelligence.

4.1. The level of emotional intelligence of students in form 2 and 4

According to Table 4, the highest mean for the construct of self-awareness for the level of emotional intelligence of students is ($m=3.23$) in the item number 4. It is apparent that the students in the second and fourth grades are aware of their own strengths and flaws. The lowest mean in this construct is ($m=2.98$), in item number 2, where they are aware that their feelings influence their behavior. In the context of this study, it shows that most students believe that understanding their own strengths and weaknesses is one of the most important ways to be self-aware. On the other hand, most students do not agree that their feelings have influenced their behavior.

Table 4. The level of emotional intelligence of students (Self-awareness)

Item	Self-awareness construct	Mean	Standard deviation (SD)
1	I know why I'm angry.	3.07	0.71
2	I am aware that feelings influence my behavior.	2.98	0.71
3	I realized my life's purpose.	3.02	0.76
4	I am aware of my strengths and weaknesses.	3.23	0.74
5	I learn from experience.	3.11	0.84

Based on Table 5, it is evident that item number 11 has the highest mean for the self-regulation construct, which measures students' emotional intelligence, at ($m=3.17$). It is evident that students in forms 2 and 4 are willing to own up to mistakes when they occur because of specific circumstances. Since they are confident that their actions are correct, the lowest mean in this construct ($m=2.50$), is in item number 7. What can be concluded through this finding is that most students can regulate themselves because they can admit their own mistakes. In addition, most students do not believe that they are too confident to do something.

Table 5. The level of emotional intelligence of students (Self-regulation)

Item	Self-regulation construct	Mean	Standard deviation
6	I can joke.	2.83	0.89
7	I'm sure it's the right thing to do.	2.50	0.79
8	I dare to voice my opinion.	2.66	0.86
9	I can make decisions.	2.81	0.75
10	I can manage stress well.	2.90	0.72
11	I am willing to admit my own mistakes.	3.17	0.76

According to Table 6, the highest mean for the construct of self-motivation for the students' level of emotional intelligence is in item number 12, where (m=3.14), as can be seen from Table 4. It is obvious that the form 2 and 4 students are engaged in serious work. This implies that they will do their utmost to complete whatever tasks are assigned to them. The lowest mean in this construct, (m=2.30), is seen in item number 15, where respondents acknowledge that they consider their preferences before acting. In a nutshell, most students believe that the motivation within them will come out if they pursue something they believe in more seriously. On the other hand, they are not confident that they do something by thinking about the impacts and implications first.

Table 6. The level of emotional intelligence of students (Self-motivation)

Item	Self-motivational construct	Mean	Standard deviation
12	I do things seriously.	3.14	0.75
13	I do my work regularly.	2.92	0.67
14	I can do multiple tasks at one time.	2.42	0.84
15	Before acting I think according to priorities.	2.30	0.70
16	I always strive to improve performance.	3.08	0.66
17	I can encourage others to achieve success.	2.69	0.88
18	I strive to achieve my goals despite obstacles.	3.08	0.67

Based on Table 7, it is evident that item number 22, where (m=3.27), has the highest mean for the concept of empathy for the students' emotional intelligence level. It is evident that form 2 and 4 students are not able to watch someone who has problems or is hurt by others. For question number 24, (m=2.32) shows they think that the suffering from others is not interesting for them, has the lowest mean in this construct. Summarily, it demonstrates that occasionally most of the students do not put themselves to know about the suffering of others but rather feel sad when they see something of that suffering. But most of them are also convinced that their empathic disposition might be exhibited through their concern for someone who gets hurt by somebody more powerful.

Table 7. The level of emotional intelligence of students (Empathy)

Item	Empathy construct	Mean	Standard deviation
19	I believe every problem can be overcome.	3.22	0.71
20	I am willing to listen to what others have to say.	3.19	0.73
21	I understand the needs of friends.	3.07	0.82
22	It saddens me to see weak people being hurt by more powerful people.	3.27	0.78
23	I am motivated to help someone when I see them suffering or in trouble.	3.07	0.66
24	The suffering or hardship of others does not attract me.	2.32	0.92
25	I cried when watching sad stories.	2.39	1.00

Based in Table 8, the highest mean for the construct of social skills for students' degree of emotional intelligence is in question number 23, where (m=3.29). It obviously demonstrates that the students can establish positive ties with their peers. It demonstrates that even in their forties, they have faith in their friends. The lowest mean in this construct is (m=2.77), which can be seen in item number 27 where they are able to hold effective group conversations. In a nutshell, most of the students believe that it is difficult for them to have a good discussion with their peers and their surroundings. But most of them also believe that they can create more appreciation towards their friendships.

As presented in Table 9, The maximum value was successfully recorded is k=5.0 for each EI construct. This means that for each of the five categories of intelligence constructs, at least one respondent gave the highest agreement, i.e., strongly agreed. Likewise, the minimum value was recorded at varying values, with the lowest minimum value reported on the self-control construct (k=1.60) and the most significant minimum value recorded on the social skills construct (k=2.14). The highest mean based on 5

types of EIs is self-regulation ($m=3.54$). This means, students know that self-regulation is an important element when they are at school. For example, they know how to present their ideas and views to the public. Otherwise, the lowest mean is ($m=3.08$), where it was recorded on self-awareness construct. At a young age, students understand how to manage themselves because they believe that their emotions influence their behaviors.

Table 8. The level of emotional intelligence of students (Social skills)

Item	Social skills construct	Mean	Standard deviation
26	I am able to convince others.	2.94	0.80
27	I am able to conduct group discussions in an effective manner.	2.77	0.84
28	I can tolerate everyone.	3.07	0.62
29	I can share information with others.	3.06	0.83
30	I can accept other people's opinions.	2.97	0.70
31	I am willing to lead when needed.	2.97	0.70
32	I am able to maintain good relationships with friends.	3.29	0.92

Table 9. Level of emotional intelligence based on five types of intelligence of students

Emotional intelligence	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
Self-awareness	108	1.60	5.00	3.08	0.60
Self-regulation	108	1.83	5.00	3.54	0.52
Self-motivation	108	2.00	5.00	3.31	0.47
Empathy	108	1.71	5.00	3.14	0.48
Social skills	108	2.14	5.00	3.45	0.60

4.2. Gender differences in emotional intelligence among form 2 and form 4 students

According to the Table 10, there is no significant difference in the mean of EI between the male and female genders. It means that the P value of 0.27 is greater than 0.05, indicating that the p value is significant at the 95% confidence level and thus the null hypothesis is accepted. When researchers dig a little further, the mean score difference between males and females is only 0.09. This demonstrates that both groups have nearly identical emotional intelligence. As a result, it can be stated that the emotional intelligence of male and female students at SMK Tembangau is approximately equivalent.

In the perspective of practical implications, this revealed that the element of gender does not have a big influence in shaping an individual's EI. However, it is due to the individual's personality aspect. If an individual demonstrates positive personalities such as always socializing, being able to manage oneself well, showing up high motivation, and having clear objectives and vision, thus they will succeed in enhancing their emotional intelligence. On the other side, if they have do not have personalities, then their emotional intelligence is also declining. In terms of individual performance in education, those who exhibit success in learning are those who have a positive EI.

Table 10. The mean difference in emotional intelligence between genders through t-test analysis (N=108)

Gender	n	Mean	Standard deviation	t-value	Sig (2-tailed)
Male	54	2.99	2.99		
Female	54	2.90	2.90	1.15	0.27

$P > 0.05$ (significant at the level 95%) = The null hypothesis is accepted

4.3. The possibility whether there is a significant relationship between aspects of emotional intelligence and big five personality towards form 2 and form 4 student

The results of the overall hypothesis, as shown in Table 11, it clearly illustrated that there is a substantial positive association between the variables of EI and BFP. The Pearson coefficient (r) is 0.674, and the p value is less than 0.001, which is less than 0.05 ($r=0.674$, $p < 0.001$). This suggests that there is a link between the emotional intelligence and personality of students in the second and fourth grades at SMK Tembangau in Bera, Pahang. This happened to students who demonstrated positive personalities such as openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism in school by demonstrating good EI in five areas namely self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy, and social skills. This demonstrates that a good personality is something that should exhibit since it can promote their attitude to increase emotional intelligence while learning. Based on the Figure 2, it shows that the positivity built by an individual through EI will help them build positivity in their personality. This shows that positive personality can be shown by students in school if they improve their emotional intelligence constantly.

Table 11. Relationship between big five personality and emotional intelligence through correlation analysis

		Emotional intelligence	Big five personality
Emotional intelligence	Pearson correlation	1	.674**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001
	N	108	108
Big five personality	Pearson correlation	.674**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	
	N	108	108

** . The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 2. The relationship between the positivity of EI in improving the positivity of BFP of an individual

5. DISCUSSION

The descriptive analysis indicated that the self-regulation construct had the highest mean score in the area of EI ($m=3.54$) when compared to the other four constructs. Based on the past study, the methods by which students take charge of their own learning and the strategies they devise to support this learning are described in self-regulated learning [52], where they concluded that students with strong self-regulation demonstrate a high level of social support, which has affected them to have higher EI in their learning. This indicates that a student's ability to regulate their personality during studying is outstanding, and that this ability is inversely related to their level of confidence. When compared to their peers who exhibit less self-regulation in the classroom, self-regulated students are more likely to seek out information [53], advice [54], and positive learning environments [55]. It means, students' ability to regulate themselves in class also will assist them to understand particular restrictions in the classroom. Failure to manage oneself in groups of friends or teachers will encourage them to engage in undesirable behaviors such as vandalism, fights, absenteeism, and so on. It is important for a student to manage self-regulation well so that they can become a more systematic person in the future. Learning self-regulated skills can help students become independent and responsible in their own learning by incorporating them into their learning processes [56]. Therefore, the teacher's responsibility in improving self-monitoring skills of students in the classroom is a very serious need so that they can adapt when they enter adulthood.

Otherwise, the lowest mean for EI is self-awareness where ($m=3.08$). When asked if they agreed with the statement that self-awareness towards their environment is important, the majority of the respondents did not respond favorably. They are unaware of their life's purpose and are not aware of their ability to impact others. Students who lack self-awareness do so for a variety of reasons. Julianto *et al.* [57] revealed that students' lack of ability to respond and be creative in the classroom was caused by their nervousness and preoccupation with others' opinions of their peers. However, this study additionally demonstrated that if they are given self-awareness training, their awareness will rise since it pushes them to better adapt to their surroundings. On the other hand, a different finding by Diadanda [58] asserted that a variety of past experiences, including theft, interpersonal conflict, sexual assault, and others, contribute to student issues that result in a lack of awareness. This is due to the role of peers who have affected their personalities. This study has explained the implication that students' self-awareness will become better if they obtain a positive effect from their friendship. Hence, teachers' contribution to increasing students' awareness at school is essential. This is due to the fact that if they are conscious of their role in society, they will take care to build strong relationships with their teachers, friends, family, and other people. Thus, self-awareness is the key to maximizing youth opportunities for self-growth and development in the future.

Moving on to the highest mean for items in five different constructs is the item number 32 ($m=3.29$), where they think they can retain an authentic relationship with their pals. Schmidt [59] asserted that allowing time and providing opportunity for students to interact meaningfully in the classroom is a

fantastic strategy to promote the growth of social networks. If a person wants to learn something easily both in school and outside of school, certainly a person's relationship with other people can influence them to do that. If they are inspired by positive things, of course the results they get will be more positive. Additionally, friendships are crucial for aiding people in adjusting to a new social context [60]. As a result, it is critical for the community, particularly parents and teachers, to counsel adolescents to form strong peer relationships. Making error of choosing friends in early years of school increases the likelihood of being a terrible student. There are multiple characteristics for friends that teenagers seek, including someone who is compassionate, outgoing, and efficient [61]. To ensure adolescents can adjust to society's acceptance of their potential, they must be someone who meets those characteristics and is quickly noticed by those around them.

Interestingly to reveal the second lowest mean for items in five different constructs is the item number 25 ($m=2.39$), where most respondents believe that they have an empathic attitude when they see tragic stories. School students have a strong sense of pity when they witness tragedy, suffering, injustice, pain, or unhappiness in the lives of others. While some researchers contend that empathy increases well-being, others contend that it causes social retreat and exhaustion [62]. Returning to one's intention, it is important to instill a sense of compassion in others from an early age in order to prevent bad things from happening to someone who is truly in need. Concern and empathy between human beings are required in social life. The Messenger of Muhammad also encouraged his followers to care for one another's fellow creatures of God and to collaborate to help one another. Being social and helping others is a universal teaching that is encouraged by all religions [63]. It is necessary for the community to have a positive attitude towards one another, yet reacting too freely will readily give opportunities for others to exploit. It is vital to have empathy for the plights of others, but empathy for oneself should take precedence.

The intelligence of success, EI, differs between men and women [64]. It can be proven that overall, the study's findings demonstrate that there is no a substantial difference in the mean score between male ($m=2.99$) and female ($m=2.90$) students' levels of emotional intelligence. This study's outcomes can be observed in the t-test analysis, which shows negligible results ($\text{sig}=0.09$). When it comes to emotional intelligence, male and female students are similar. There is a study conducted on high school students in Iran whose findings show that EI in 17-year-old 11th grade school females compared with males from six different districts [65]. On the other hand, in India, 10th graders, the EI of female students was demonstrated to be higher in comparison with their male counterparts [66]. Even though every student has a distinct or even a similar level of EI, society must nonetheless provide them with encouragement and support if they are to continue to progress. It becomes an implication for teachers that the development of students is followed by the knowledge they acquire at school. Every student, then, has the chance to pursue a decent education in order to raise their EI level, which will pave the way for a better future.

Moving on to the association between the BFP theory and EI, the Pearson correlation test reveals that the P value is less than 0.05. It demonstrates how the values of the two variables complement each other. The link between these two variables will also boost an individual's academic performance potential. Students' emotional intelligence abilities and personalities have an impact on how successfully they study and how productive they are [40]. This demonstrates that responders who exhibit a favorable emotional reaction will have a more positive disposition. A person who cannot grow his emotions correctly, on the other hand, causes his personality to develop poorly. Matchimanon discovered the link between EI and personality [67]. The findings revealed a significant link between overall emotional intelligence and personality attributes. Previous study suggests that the interplay between EI and BFP has a significant impact on an individual. When attempting to accomplish one's goals, a person's personality reflects how that person handles both positive and negative emotions, demanding life events, disputes, and interpersonal connections. These are the areas that EI, and particularly Trait EI, has an impact on [26]. Summarily, it is important to encourage students to increase their emotional level when they are at home or at school. This will lead them to become a better person in the future.

6. CONCLUSION

This study sheds new light on the value of helping students to experience healthy emotional development for parents, teachers, and students themselves. Students that have strong emotional intelligence will be able to change their attitudes and behaviors, which will help them develop a good character and a standout personality. If seen in developed countries such as the United Kingdom, Australia, Finland, and Singapore, their education systems empower students through positive actions at home and at school. Therefore, the school in particular, needs to implement various interesting activities such as motivational activities, counseling, peer programs, or visit programs to educational centers so that the development of students with good personalities can be achieved through the excellence of their emotional level at school. Dropping out of students to participate in beneficial activities will influence them to participate in activities that are not beneficial and this will close their future to achieve their desired goals. As a result, teachers must

play an essential part in supervising student movement and providing them with varied activities and interesting interventions that can help them develop emotionally. This can help them develop more aggressively in the future.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. M. Majzud, *Psikologi Perkembangan Untuk Bakal Guru*. Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia: Fajar Bakti (in Malay), 1993.
- [2] A. Ishak, M. Rahmat, S. Shahrani, N. F. A. Zainal, and F. A. Rahman, "Personality compatibility with computer science and information technology program selection," *Jurnal Teknologi*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 49–55, 2014, doi: 10.11113/jt.v68.1831.
- [3] S. Mammadov, "Big Five personality traits and academic performance: A meta-analysis," *Journal of Personality*, vol. 90, no. 2, pp. 222–255, 2021, doi: 10.1111/jopy.12663.
- [4] C. Lechner, S. Anger, and B. Rammstedt, "Socioemotional skills in education and beyond: Recent evidence and future research avenues," in *Research Handbook on the Sociology of Education*, Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing, 2019, pp. 1–49.
- [5] L. Borghans, B. H. Golsteyn, J. J. Heckman, and J. E. Humphries, "What grades and achievement tests measure," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 113, no. 47, pp. 13354–13359, 2016, doi:10.1073/pnas.1601135113.
- [6] J. Zhang and M. Ziegler, "How do the Big Five influence scholastic performance? A Big Five-narrow traits model or a double mediation model," *Learning and Individual Differences*, vol. 50, pp. 93–102, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.lindif.2016.07.011.
- [7] M. Spengler, M. Brunner, R. Martin, and O. Lüdtke, "The role of personality in predicting (change in) students' academic success across four years of secondary school," *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 95–103, 2016, doi: 10.1027/1015-5759/a000330
- [8] H. Fallahzadeh, "The relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement in medical science students in Iran," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 30, pp. 1461–1466, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.10.283.
- [9] E. J. Austin, D. H. Saklofske, and V. Egan, "Personality, well-being and health correlates of trait emotional intelligence," *Personality and Individual Differences*, vol. 38, pp. 547–558, 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.paid.2004.05.009
- [10] F. Yusoff, A. Desa, N. B. A. Kadir, and R. M. A. R., "A study of the relationship between eq and personality among lecturers at a research university," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 114, pp. 351–354, 2014.
- [11] J. Xu and M. Choi, "Can emotional intelligence increase the positive psychological capital and life satisfaction of Chinese university students?" *Behavior Science*, vol. 13, no. 7, pp. 1–18, 2023, doi: 10.3390/bs13070614
- [12] A. Alegre, N. Pérez-Escoda, and E. López-Cassá, "The relationship between trait Emotional Intelligence and personality. Is trait EI really anchored within the big five, big two and big one framework?" *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 10, no. 866, pp. 1–9, 2019, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00866.
- [13] J. C. Pérez-González, and M. J. Sánchez-Ruiz, "Trait emotional intelligence anchored within the big five, big two and big one framework," *Personality and Individual Differences*, vol. 65, pp. 53–58, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.paid.2014.01.021.
- [14] J. Jaise, K. V. Shetty, U. Baruah, U. Bamney, and G. M. Sachetha, "Emotional intelligence and personality among undergraduate students in a rural district of South India," *Current Medicine Research and Practice*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 163–166, 2023, doi: 10.4103/cmrrp.cmrrp_105_22.
- [15] A. Kirch, M. Schnitzius, F. Mess, and S. Spengler, "Who are our students? Understanding students' personality for refined and targeted physical education. A Scoping Review," *Frontiers in Sports and Active Living*, vol. 1, no. 32, pp. 1–20, 2019, doi: 10.3389/fspor.2019.00031.
- [16] M. Richardson, C. Abraham, and R. Bond, "Psychological correlates of university students' academic performance: A systematic review and meta-analysis," *Psychological Bulletin*, vol. 138, pp. 353–387, 2012, doi: 10.1037/a0026838.
- [17] M. C. O'Connor and S.V. Paunonen, "Big Five personality predictors of post-secondary academic performance," *Personality and Individual Differences*, vol. 43, pp. 971–990, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.paid.2007.03.017
- [18] A. E. Poropat, "A meta-analysis of the five-factor model of personality and academic performance," *Psychological Bulletin*, vol. 135, pp. 22–338, 2009, doi: 10.1037/a0014996.
- [19] P. Dhani and T. Sharma, "Emotional Intelligence and personality; it's relationship in Indian context," *Prabandhan Indian Journal of Management*, vol. 10, no. 9, pp. 39–52, 2017, doi: 10.17010/pijom/2017/v10i9/118241.
- [20] P. Dhani and T. Sharma, "Relationship between emotional intelligence and personality: A study in Indian context," *International Business Management*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 1133–1139, doi:10.3923/ibm.2017.1133.1139.
- [21] S. Murmu and N. Neelam, "Impact of emotional intelligence and personality traits on managing team performance in virtual interface," *Asian Journal of Business Ethics*, vol. 11(Suppl 1), pp. 33–53, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s13520-022-00154-1.
- [22] P. Salovey and R. Straus, "Emotional intelligence, personality, and the perceived quality of social relationships," *Personality and Individual Differences*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 641–658, 2003, doi: 10.1016/S0191-8869(02)00242-8.
- [23] M. H. Jafri, "Moderating role of Emotional Intelligence on personality– employee creativity relationship," *Management and Labour Studies*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 15–30, 2020, doi: 10.1177/0258042X19890243.
- [24] G. Saucier and L. R. Goldberg, "The language of personality: Lexical perspectives a the five-factor model," in J. S. Wiggings, Ed., *The Five-Factor Model of Personality Theoretical Perspective*. New York: The Guilford Press, 1996, pp. 22–50.
- [25] R. R. McCrae and O. P. John, "An introduction to the five-factor model and its applications," *Journal of Personality*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 175–215, 1992, doi: 10.1111/j.1467-6494.1992.tb00970.x.
- [26] V. Kumar and G. Tankha, "Association between the big five and trait emotional intelligence among college students," *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, vol. 16, pp. 915–925, 2023, doi: 10.2147/PRBM.S400058.
- [27] E. Ang, "Relationship between emotional intelligence and "big five" personality among primary school teachers in Kota Tinggi district." Master thesis, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://eprints.utm.my/78561>.
- [28] B. Ghiabi and M. A. Behsarat, "An investigation of the relationship between Personality dimensions and emotional intelligence," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 30, pp. 416–420, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.10.082.

- [29] A. Duran, N. Extremera, and L. Rey, "Self-reported emotional intelligence burnout and engagement among staff in service for people with intellectual disabilities," *Psychological Reports*, vol. 95, no. 2, pp. 386–390, 2004, doi: 10.2466/pr0.95.2.386-390.
- [30] P. M. Grehan, R. Flanagan, and R. G. Malgady, "Successful graduate students: The roles of personality traits and emotional intelligence," *Psychology in the Schools*, vol. 48, no. 4, pp. 317–331, 2011, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.20556>.
- [31] M. Atta, M. Ather, and M. Bano, "Emotional intelligence and personality traits among university teachers: relationship and gender difference," *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, vol. 4, no. 17, pp. 253–259.
- [32] M. Vianello, K. Schnabel, S. Natarajan, and A. Brian, "Gender differences in implicit and explicit personality traits," *SSRN Electronic Journal*, pp. 1–22, 2013, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.2249080.
- [33] Z. Zali and S. Surat, "Identifying the big five personality factors towards learning performance: A Systematic Review," *Malaysian Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. e001271, doi: <https://doi.org/10.47405/mjssh.v7i2.1271>.
- [34] M. N. McCredie, and J. F. Kurtz, "Prospective prediction of academic performance in college using self- and informant-rated personality traits," *Journal of Research in Personality*, vol. 85, pp. e103911, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jrp.2019.103911.
- [35] S. K. Kertechian, "Conscientiousness as a key to success for academic achievement among French university students enrolled in management studies," *The International Journal of Management Education*, vol. 16, pp. 154–165, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.ijme.2018.02.003.
- [36] J. R. Wojciechowska, J. Wojciechowski, and M. Stolarski, "Do time perspectives predict school performance beyond intelligence and personality?" *Personality and Individual Differences*, vol. 172, pp. e110594, doi: 10.1016/j.paid.2020.110594.
- [37] I. Soric, Z. Penezic, and I. Buric, "The Big Five personality traits, goal orientations, and academic achievement," *Learning and Individual Differences*, vol. 54, pp. 126–134, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.lindif.2017.01.024.
- [38] K. A. Papageorgiou *et al.*, "Personality, Behavioral strengths and difficulties and performance of adolescents with high achievements in science, literature, art and sports," *Personality and Individual Differences*, vol. 160, p. e109917, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.paid.2020.109917.
- [39] M. M. Naqshbandi, S. Ainin, N. I. Jaafar and L. M. Shuib, "Facebook or to Face Book? An investigation of how academic performance of different personalities is affected through the intervention of Facebook usage," *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 75, pp. 167–176, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.chb.2017.05.012.
- [40] X. Dong, O. A. Kalugina, D. G. Vasbieva, and A. Rafi, "Emotional intelligence and personality traits based on academic performance," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 13, pp. 1–9, 2022, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.894570.
- [41] D. A. Major, J. E. Turner, and T. D. Fletcher, "Linking proactive personality and the Big Five to motivation to learn and development activity," *Journal of Applied Psychology*, vol. 91, no. 4, pp. 927–935, 2006, doi: 10.1037/0021-9010.91.4.927.
- [42] B. Parasuraman, "Social science research debates: Researcher experiences," *Jurnal Kemanusiaan*, vol. 9, no. 2, p. 46, 2017.
- [43] J. W. Creswell, *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*, 4th ed, Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publication Ltd, 2014.
- [44] Y. Ahmad and N. M. Yusof, "Competence of cultural diversity among teachers diversity of ethnicity in national secondary schools in Malaysia," *Jurnal Kepimpinan Pendidikan*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 1–13, 2015.
- [45] M. Sathiyaseelan, "Research instruments," *Indian Journal of Continuing Nursing Education*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 57–60, 2015, [Online]. Available: <https://www.ijcne.org/text.asp?2015/16/2/57/284862>.
- [46] S. Ropa and M. S. Rani, "Questionnaire designing for a survey," *The Journal of Indian Orthodontic Society*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 37–41, 2012, doi: 10.5005/jp-journals-10021-1104.
- [47] O. P. John, E. M. Donahue, and R. L. Kentle, *The Big Five Inventory - Versions 4a and 54*. California, Berkeley, Institute of Personality and Social Research, 1991.
- [48] A. M. A. Rahman, "Effects of Cognitive Behavioral Group Counseling in treating bullying behaviors among high school students," Doctoral Dissertation, National Malaysia University, Selangor, 2004.
- [49] Center for Research and Innovation Management, *Research Ethics Guidelines*, Kedah, Malaysia: Universiti Utara Malaysia.
- [50] Department of Personal Data Protection, "Personal Data Protection Act 2010," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pdp.gov.my/jpdpv2/laws-of-malaysia-pdpa/personal-data-protection-act-2010/?lang=en>.
- [51] Z. Ali and S. B. Bhaskar, "Basic statistical tools in research and data analysis," *Indian Journal of Anaesthesia*, vol. 60, no. 9, pp. 662–669, 2016, doi: 10.4103/0019-5049.190623.
- [52] C. Yot-Domínguez and C. Marcelo, "University students' self-regulated learning using digital technologies," *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, vol. 14, no. 38, pp. 1–18, 2017, doi: 10.1186/s41239-017-0076-8.
- [53] G. Clarebout, H. Horz, and W. Schnotz, "The relations between self-regulation and the embedding of support in learning environments," *Educational Technology Research and Development*, vol. 58, no. 5, pp. 573–587, 2010.
- [54] A. B. de Bruin, K. W. Thiede, and G. Camp, "Generating keywords improves metacomprehension and self-regulation in elementary and middle school children," *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, vol. 109, no. 3, pp. 294–310, 2001.
- [55] A. S. Labuhn, B. J. Zimmerman, and M. Hasselhorn, "Enhancing students' self-regulation and mathematics performance: The influence of feedback and self-evaluative standards," *Metacognition and Learning*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 173–194, 2010.
- [56] S. Sahranavard, M. R. Miri, and H. Salehiniya, "The relationship between self-regulation and educational performance in students," *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, vol. 28, no. 7, pp. 1–5, 2018, doi: 10.4103/jehp.jehp_93_18.
- [57] B. Julianto, W. Wagimin, and M. Muslim, "The Effectiveness of Self-Awareness Training to Improve Students' Self-Adjustment," (in Indonesian), *CONSILIUM: Jurnal Program Studi Bimbingan dan Konseling*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1–5, 2016, [Online]. Available: <https://jurnal.fkip.uns.ac.id/index.php/councilium/article/view/11054>.
- [58] A. Diananda, "Adolescent Psychology and Its Problems," (in Indonesian), *Istighna*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 116–133, 2018, doi: 10.33853/istighna.v1i1.20.
- [59] S. J. Schmidt, "The importance of friendships for academic success," *Journal of Food Science Education*, vol. 19, pp. 2–5, 2020, doi: 10.1111/1541-4329.12176.
- [60] V. M. Buote *et al.*, "The importance of friends: Friendship and adjustment among 1st-year university students," *Journal of Adolescent Research*, vol. 22, no. 6, pp. 665–689, 2007, doi: 10.1177/0743558407306344.
- [61] A. R. Anderson and J. B. Fowers, "An exploratory study of friendship characteristics and their relations with hedonic and eudaimonic well-being," *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 260–280, 2019, doi: 10.1177/0265407519861152.
- [62] S. H. Konrath, E. H. O'Brien and C. Hsing, "Changes in dispositional empathy in American college students over time: A meta-analysis," *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 180–198, 2011, doi: 10.1177/1088868310377395.
- [63] E. N. Tiyas, "The Influence of Empathy on Caring in Adolescents," (in Indonesian), Master Thesis, Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang, Indonesia, 2017.
- [64] M. Meshkat and R. Nejadi, "Does Emotional Intelligence Depend on Gender? A Study on Undergraduate English Majors of Three Iranian Universities," *SAGE Open*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1–8, 2017, doi: 10.1177/2158244017725796.

- [65] R. Zohrevand, "A comparison of self-efficacy, emotional intelligence, gender beliefs, gender satisfaction of females and males in predicting their academic achievement," *Motalleat Ravanshenakhti*, vol. 6, pp. 46–73, 2010.
- [66] D. Joshi and I. Dutta, "Emotional intelligence among secondary students: Role of gender and type of school," *MIER Journal of Educational Studies, Trends & Practices*, vol. 4, pp. 167–182, 2014, doi: 10.52634/mier/2014/v4/i2/1468.
- [67] A. Duran, N. Extremera, L. Rey, P. Fernández-Berrocal, and F. M. Montalbán, "Predicting academic burnout and engagement in educational settings: Assessing the incremental validity of perceived emotional intelligence beyond perceived stress and general self-efficacy," *Psicothema*, vol. 18 (Suppl.), pp. 158–164, 2006.

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